

ISic0804

Dedication of a statue to Ceres, by Iulius Acilius Hermes, sevir

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

marble (white)

Object

statue base

Editor

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Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2019-07-11

Last Change

2019-07-15 - Jonathan Prag made further revisions following fresh autopsy and photography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 8 September 1970; found on the floor of the west portico, between rooms 2 and 3

Coordinates

37.998037, 14.262643

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20194

Physical Description

The inscription is incised on the face of the ovoid base which forms part of the same block from which is carved the statue of Ceres, 1.7m high. The base is 56 cm wide, 31.5 cm deep and 7.5-10.5 cm high.

Dimensions

Height 7.5-10.5 cm

Width 56 cm

Depth 31.5 cm

Layout

The Latin text is engraved over two lines (letters c.20 mm high, but of uneven height), to a maximum length of 52 cm.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters show some irregularity, with fairly pronounced serifs, and lengthy tails to the letter R. The first two words are separated from the rest by a space; an interpunct is visible at the end of the dedicant's name, and the final abbreviated phrase is separated from the rest by a large hedera (ivy leaf). The letter I in line 1 is frequently taller than the rest (but so too is the first L in line 1); the final I of line 1 is somewhat irregularly carved.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 18-25 mm

Line 2: 19-23 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1-2: 7-15 mm

Text

1. Cereri sacr(um) (vac.undefined) Iulius Acilius Her

2. mes · pro honor(e) seviratus □ d(eae) d(onum) d(edit)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

alternatively: d(ecreto) d(ecurionum) d(edit); d(edit) d(e)d(icavit)

Translation (en)

Sacred to Ceres. Iulius Acilius Hermes, to commemorate the honour of his sevirate. He gave this as a gift to the goddess (or: He gave it by decree of the town council; or He gave it and dedicated it).

Commentary

The statue has been carefully analysed by Portale (2009: 80-87), who highlights the association of Ceres with imperial ideology (key traits of fertility, abundance and good fortune, and associations with female members of the imperial house), and can be dated stylistically to the late Antonine period (i.e. the 180s or 190s AD). The form of the inscription is entirely compatible with such a date (the text could belong to the second or third century AD). The statue may have stood, originally, in an elevated niche in room six or seven of the portico (Portale 2009: 80 n.30), which would have facilitated the reading of the inscription. A similar, although slightly earlier, acephalous statue was found in the same area of the portico (Portale 2009: 82 fig.8) and may be associated with the dedication to Concord by another sevir (ISic0768 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0768>]).

The gens Acilius may be attested in another fragmentary text from the agora, ISic0801 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0801>] (for the presence of the name in Sicily, see Facella 2006: 287 and 293; Prestianni Giallombardo 2012: 195 n.116).

Digital identifiers:

TM 175724

EDR 075546

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